

Paradise Lost

The origins of Wonder Woman

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the creation of the comics character Wonder Woman by the psychologist William Moulton Marston in the 1940s. Wonder Woman roots can be traced back to the American feminism of the 1910-20s. The analysis of selected Wonder Woman stories shows their connection with the women's condition in the World War II. The spirit of the first stories surfaces again in the second wave of the feminist movement and in the popular culture.

Keywords: Wonder Woman, William Moulton Marston, Comics, Popular Culture, Feminism in the United States.

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And now for something completely different

In the United States comics appeared as drawn strips (Strips or Funnies) in newspapers at the end of the 19th century.¹ Press barons, like Joseph Pulitzer and William Randolph Hearst, introduced them to win over a wider public, including immigrants. Thanks to artists such as Richard Outcault (the author of Yellow Kid), Winsor McCay (Little Nemo), Lyonel Feininger (Kinder-Kids) and George Herriman (Krazy Kat) Strips became very popular, with Sunday colour supplements. A system of agencies (strip syndicates) were in charge of the distribution to newspapers in the various States.

In a short time, Strips were reprinted as comic books of various format; *Famous Funnies* (Eastern Color 1934) fixed a standard: color comic books of about 10.5x7 inches, sold at 10 cents.² One step still remained to make: the production of comic books that were not reprints, but new stories which did not result in a few strips. The first issue of *Action Comics* (National Periodicals 1938) with the character of Superman started the Golden Age of comics.³ In 1939 *Detective Comics*⁴ No. 27 launched the vigilante Batman. Soon the best-selling comic book names exceeded one million copies. The subgenres published were western, mystery, comic or romantic, but the main characters of the most popular stories were super-heroes. Besides Superman, we remember Captain Marvel (Fawcett, 1941)⁵ and Captain America (Marvel, 1941).

In this panorama of action and virile strength there were relatively few female protagonists.⁶ Until December 1941, when All-American Publications by Charles Gaines published "Introducing Wonder Woman" in *All-Star Comics* No 8.

At last, in a world torn by the hatreds and wars of men, appears a woman to whom the problems and feats of men are mere child's play....As lovely as Aphrodite—as wise as Athena—with the speed of Mercury and the strength of Hercules—she is known only as WONDER WOMAN, but who she is, or whence she came, nobody knows!⁷

At the beginning of the adventure, Steve Trevor, an American aviator, crashes on "an uncharted isle amidst a vast ocean". While the pilot is rescued and cured, Hippolyte, the queen of the isle and of the Amazons who live in, tells her daughter Diana an amazing story: "In the days of Ancient Greece, many centuries ago, we Amazons were the foremost nation in the world. In Amazonia,

¹ For an analysis see David Manning WHITE and Robert Herman ABEL, *The Funnies. An American Idiom*. By Various Authors. With Illustrations. (xv. 304. Free Press of Glencoe: New York: Collier-Macmillan: London, 1963).

² Roger Sabin, *Comics, comix & graphic novels/a history of comic art*, (New York: Phaidon press, 1996) 20, 35.

³ They lasted until about 1950; after a market crisis it was followed by the Silver Age (started around 1956), Bronze Age etc., according to the different classifications of experts.

⁴ The current DC Comics (formerly National Comics) publisher was named after Detective Comics. Publishers with several business names published the various comic book names. Since 1940 (*Action Comics* No.23) the covers had showed the logo "A DC publication" (since 1941 "A Superman DC publication"), however, meant as a seal of quality and not as a publishing brand, Levitz, Paul, and Josh Baker, *The Golden Age of DC Comics 1935-1956*, 2013.

⁵ For a time Captain Marvel's sales exceeded those of Superman: Larry Tye, *Superman: the high-flying history of America's most enduring hero*, 1st ed (New York: Random House, 2012) 54.

⁶ We remember Sheena, a jungle queen created by Will Eisner and Jerry Iger; Miss Fury (1941-1952), Scripts and drawings of a woman, June Tarpe Mills <http://comicbookplus.com/?cid=3266>; Lady Luck by Will Eisner (like Ford Davis) <http://comicbookplus.com/?cid=1313>; Invisible Scarlet O'Neil by Russell Stamm (1940) <http://comicbookplus.com/?cid=1955>, first published as strips in newspapers and then in comic books; Mike Madrid, ed., *Divas, dames & daredevils: lost heroines of golden age comics* (Ashland, OR: Exterminating Angel Press, 2013).

⁷ "Introducing Wonder Woman" —*All-Star Comics* #8, December 1941; The first stories are reprinted in William Moulton Marston et al., *Wonder Woman, the Golden Age omnibus* Vol.1-3 (DC Comics 2016-2018); William Moulton Marston and H. G Peter, *Wonder Woman: The Complete Dailies 1944-1945*, The Library of American Comics (San Diego, CA: IDW Publishing, 2014).

women ruled and all was well.” But, then, Hercules defeated the Amazons by deception and enslaved them.⁸ They begged the goddess Aphrodite who freed and guided them:

it was Aphrodite’s condition that we leave the man made world and establish a new world of our own! Aphrodite also decreed that we must always wear these bracelets fashioned by our captors, as a reminder that we must always keep aloof from men... We found Paradise Island and settled here to build a New World!...we Amazons have been able to far surpass the inventions of the so-called man-made civilization! We are not only stronger and wiser than men—but our weapons are better—our flying machines are further advanced!

Trevor informs the queen that war and dictatorships threaten the world; Aphrodite and Athena, the guardian goddesses of Amazons, give their answer:

You must deliver him [Trevor] back to America — to help fight the forces of hate and oppression...you must send with him your strongest and wisest amazon—the finest of your wonder women!— for America, the last citadel of democracy, and of equal rights for women, needs your help!

The strongest and wisest of Amazons, selected in a series of competitions, turned out to be Diana, i.e. Wonder Woman. The subsequent adventures would be set mainly in America.

Since January 1942 in the new series *Sensation Comics*. Wonder Woman had the cover image – and from then on, she would always have it.

The stories were written by “Charles Moulton”. But who was this man? Where did these ideas about Greek mythology, Amazons and women’s rights, come from? What about those bracelets? To learn about all that we need to go back to the beginning of the century, first to Cambridge – Harvard University and then to New York.

Harvard

The pseudonym “Charles Moulton” combined the middle names of Maxwell Charles Gaines (the publisher, also known as Charles Gaines) and William Moulton Marston, the real author.

Marston was born in Saugus, MA on May 5, 1893. He excelled in his studies and his varied interests and around the age of 13 he met the girl he would one day marry, i.e. his clever and lively peer Sadie Elizabeth Holloway, born in the Isle of Man (UK) in 1893.⁹

Marston moved to Cambridge to enter University in September 1911. Harvard did not admit girls to its courses and Holloway enrolled in the women’s college of Mount Holyoke, South Hadley, Massachusetts. There were other things that Harvard did not admit: when *Harvard Men’s League for Woman Suffrage*, founded among others by John Reed – at the time a senior – invited the English suffragette Emmeline Pankhurst, the university did not welcome her. The lecture was then given in a theatre and maybe Marston attended it.¹⁰

Holloway’s College was “a citadel of equal rights for women”: the dean and most teachers were in favour of the female suffrage. In comics the girls from ‘Holliday College’, led by Etta Candy, will often help Wonder Woman. Holloway loved Greek and Wharton’s *Sappho*¹¹ was on her bedside table when she died, at the age of one hundred.¹²

From the beginning, Marston attended the Harvard Psychology Laboratory. Holloway worked with him; here they conceived the research on the relation of emotions to the blood pressure, the

⁸ For the myth of Amazons in classicism see e.g. Mark Morford and Robert Lenardon, *Classical Mythology* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2003) 212, 530, 564.

⁹ For biographical data the main source is Jill Lepore, *The Secret History of Wonder Woman*, (New York: Alfred A. Knopf, 2014), see also Geoffrey C. Bunn, «The Lie Detector, Wonder Woman and Liberty: The Life and Work of William Moulton Marston», *History of the Human Sciences* 10, No.1 (1st February 1997): 91–119, <https://doi.org/10.1177/095269519701000105>.

¹⁰ Lepore, Ch. 1.

¹¹ Henry Thornton Wharton, *Sappho. Memoir, Text, Selected Renderings, and a Literal Translation* (London; Chicago: J. Lane; A.C. McClurg & Co., 1898).

¹² Lepore, Ch. 31.

embryonic idea of Lie Detector, published in 1917.¹³ Some Wonder Woman cartoons depict Marston's experiment machine.

Marston and Holloway took their Bachelor Degree in 1915 and they got married in September. They enrolled in Law Faculty (Law School), at Harvard and Boston University respectively. During the war, Marston continued his experiments at the military facilities.¹⁴

Marston and Holloway graduated from law school in June 1918. In August, they took the bar exam together...In September 1919, Marston enrolled in Harvard's PhD program in philosophy and Holloway, five months pregnant, enrolled in an MA program at Radcliffe. All of the courses taken by Radcliffe graduate students were taught at Harvard's graduate school, by Harvard professors. Mr. and Mrs. Marston enrolled together for two semesters of Psychological Laboratory with Herbert Langfeld.¹⁵

Research continued and Marston took his PhD in 1921. Holloway always claimed the idea of the original experiment.

The Suffragettes, the Reds and birth control

At the beginning of the 20th century, women's suffrage was a national problem and political parties had included it in the agenda. The NAWSA (*National American Woman Suffrage Association*) had two million female members in 1916 - "an army of young Amazons"¹⁶ - and organized regular demonstrations in the capital. Margaret Sanger and her younger sister Ethel Byrne lived in New York and they were feminists, a word that was replacing the term suffragette.¹⁷ Being joined feminist and radical clubs, they saw Emma Goldman (aka *Red Emma*), Charlotte Perkins Gilman, Crystal and Max Eastman.¹⁸ The latter with John Reed published *The Masses*, "A Monthly Magazine devoted to the Interests of the Working People".¹⁹ The Masses published articles in support of woman suffrage, and the "Woman's Number" (Dec. 1911). Gilman had published *Women and Economics* (1898) and *The Man-made World* (1911): the need to free oneself from the economic dependence in a world created by men will be a recurring

¹³ William Moulton Marston, "Systolic Blood Pressure Symptoms of Deception," *Journal of Experimental Psychology* 2 (1917): 117-76. now in *American Polygraph Association*, «Polygraph, SPECIAL ISSUE WILLIAM MOULTON MARSTON» 4, n. 14 (1985): 289-320.

¹⁴ Bunn 95ff.

¹⁵ Lepore, Ch. 6, 7.

¹⁶ Anne Firor Scott e Andrew MacKay Scott, *One Half the People: The Fight for Woman Suffrage* (University of Illinois Press, 1982) 39.

¹⁷ Karen Manners Smith *New paths to power: 1890-1920* in Nancy F. Cott, ed., *No small courage: a history of women in the United States* (Oxford; New York: Oxford University Press, 2000) 398-99.

¹⁸ Blanche Wiesen Cook *FEMALE SUPPORT NETWORKS AND POLITICAL ACTIVISM: Lillian Wald, Crystal Eastman, Emma Goldman* in Nancy F. Cott e Elizabeth H. Pleck, ed., *A Heritage of her own: toward a new social history of American women*, A Touchstone book (New York: Simon and Schuster, 1979) 412ff. Some sequences of the film *Reds* by Warren Beatty (1981) can refer to this environment.

¹⁹ Visit the web site NYU <http://dlib.nyu.edu/themasses/> to see the whole collection.

theme in Wonder Woman's stories.²⁰ The utopian novel *Herland*²¹, an isolated land where only women live, who reproduce by parthenogenesis, was then published in 1915. It is an ideal society, "an undiscovered country of a strictly Amazonian nature", where war and oppression are unknown.

To us, at first, these women, unavoidably ignorant of what to us was the basic commonplace of knowledge, had seemed on the plane of children, or of savages. What we had been forced to admit, with growing acquaintance, was that they were ignorant as Plato and Aristotle were, but with a highly developed mentality quite comparable to that of Ancient Greece.

...

Three million highly intelligent women—or two million, counting only grown-ups...We thought of them as "Women," and therefore timid; but it was two thousand years since they had had anything to be afraid of, and certainly more than one thousand since they had outgrown the feeling.

...

"We try most earnestly for two powers...The two that seem to us basically necessary for all noble life: a clear, far-reaching judgment, and a strong well-used will. We spend our best efforts, all through childhood and youth, in developing these faculties, individual judgment and will."

Women had actively participated in the utopian experiences in the United States. Women like Ann Lee, leader of the Shakers — believers in God's bisexuality —; like Frances Wright, in the communities of New Harmony — founded by Robert Owen — and of Nashoba; like Jemima Wilkinson who founded the *Jerusalem* community.²²

Since 1914 Sanger had published the feminist paper *Woman Rebel*²³ and was convinced, like Ethel Byrne, that birth control was more urgent than female suffrage.²⁴ In October 1916, Sanger and Byrne opened the first hospital department for birth control in Brooklyn. Authorities closed it and seized them for breaking the New York State law that prohibited any contraceptive. Byrne went on a hunger strike where she risked dying; Sanger served thirty days in prison.²⁵

Years later, Sanger founded the *Birth Control Review*, and the *American Birth Control League*. In August 1920 the Nineteenth amendment introduced women's suffrage and in October Sanger published *Woman and the New Race*,²⁶ with a preface by Havelock Ellis that Sanger had met in the UK and whose essay "The Love Rights of Women"²⁷ had been published.

Lepore thus points out the future importance of the book:

²⁰ Charlotte Perkins Gilman, *Women and Economics: A Study of the Economic Relation Between Men and Women as a Factor In ...* (Small, Maynard, & company, 1898); *The Man-Made World: Or, Our Androcentric Culture* (Charlton Co., 1911); Carl N. Degler, «Charlotte Perkins Gilman on the Theory and Practice of Feminism», *American Quarterly* 8, n. 1 (1956): 21–39, <https://doi.org/10.2307/2710295>.

²¹ Charlotte Perkins Gilman, *Herland*. (Auckland: Floating Press, 1915). We quote from the Project Gutenberg edition at <http://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/32>

²² Mark Holloway, *Heavens on Earth: Utopian Communities in America 1680-1880*. (1951) (New York, 1966) 55-59, 114-115, 59-64.

²³ "Margaret Sanger Papers Project" (NYU) <https://www.nyu.edu/projects/sanger/>

²⁴ LINDA GORDON BIRTH CONTROL AND SOCIAL REVOLUTION in Nancy F. Cott e Elizabeth H. Pleck, ed., *A Heritage of her own: toward a new social history of American women* 445ff; Margaret Sanger, *My Fight for Birth Control* (London: Faber & Faber, 1932) 61-62.

²⁵ David M Kennedy, *Birth Control in America: The Career of Margaret Sanger* (New Haven: Yale Univ. Pr., 1976) 83-85.

²⁶ Margaret Sanger, *Woman and the New Race* (New York: Brentano's, 1920).

²⁷ Collected in Havelock Ellis, *Little Essays of Love and Virtue* (New York: George H. Doran Company, 1922), 102-115.

Years later [March 1944], when Marston hired a young woman named Joye Hummel to help him write *Wonder Woman*, Olive Byrne gave Hummel a copy of *Woman and the New Race*. Read this, she told her, and you'll know everything you need to know about *Wonder Woman*.²⁸

Sex, Lies, and Sound Film

Olive Byrne was born in February 1904; Margaret Sanger, a nurse and her elder sister helped Ethel Byrne to give birth. One night, Ethel Byrne's husband, while he was going home, heard the baby crying, took and threw her into the snow. Then, he got drunk again. Margaret Sanger rushed out to rescue her from the snow and take her home: she had created the first relationship with the future *Wonder Woman*.

In 1921 Marston taught legal psychology at American University as a professor and a director of the Psychology Department. Being an advisor of various trials, he tried unsuccessfully to introduce his Lie Detector in the courts. When the University did not renew his appointment, Marston moved to Tufts, a women's college, as an Assistant Professor of Psychology.

After her lower education, Olive Byrne had enrolled in Tufts in 1922, and followed Marston's course (1925-26) who recruited her as an assistant for a series of research on emotions.

Byrne got her BA on June 14, 1926. Meanwhile, Marston had established a relationship with Byrne: maybe that's why his job at Tufts was not renewed.

The relationship continued and Olive Byrne moved to Marston's, where she would then look after the house, while Holloway continued to work. The relationship between Olive and Elizabeth was never clear and many things were said. But it is a fact that each of them gave her child the name of the other and, after Marston's death, they always lived together.

Holloway was then editor in the New York offices of the *Encyclopaedia Britannica*; Marston contributed to the fourteenth edition the article "Analysis of Emotions".²⁹

In 1928 Marston published *The Emotions of Normal People*³⁰ where he identifies the basic emotions Dominance (D), Compliance (C), Inducement (I), Submission (S) with the relations D-C, I-S. They give rise to the complex emotions such as Appetite (desire to possess and be successful) and Love: "love (real love, not *sex appetite*), constitutes, in the human organism, the ultimate end of all activity" (q.v. 391). In the man-made world we have developed abnormal, monstrous appetites:

To satisfy them, even partially, we must have things, and more things, and to get things we are obliged to comply with the people who now possess them. They set the standards...which enforce compliance with their own thing-getting activities. (ibid.)

Love Leaders are needed to restore emotional normality. Men are not suitable for "intra-organic" (393) reasons and the task falls upon women who must first come out of the economic dependence, understand the emotional mechanisms and gain power jobs in politics and economics, whose skills can evolve "within a few generations" (394).³¹

Both Holloway and Byrne got their degrees in psychology and often collaborated with Marston. In particular many of the criticisms to sexist psychologies in *Emotions of Normal People* come from Olive Byrne's research for her Master's thesis at Columbia University.³²

Since he did not manage to get a professorship, Marston accepted to give a consultancy to Carl Laemmle, head of Universal Studios in Hollywood and for some time Marston and Byrne moved to California (January 1929).

²⁸ Lepore, Ch. 12.

²⁹ Lepore, Ch. 10, 8, 14, 16.

³⁰ William Moulton Marston, *Emotions Of Normal People* (Kegan Paul Trench Trubner And Company., Limited, 1928).

³¹ For an analysis see Matthew Brown, «Love Slaves and Wonder Women: Radical Feminism and Social Reform in the Psychology of William Moulton Marston», *Feminist Philosophy Quarterly* 2, No. 1 (8 July 2016), <https://doi.org/10.5206/fpq/2016.1.1>; and Bunn 102ff.

³² Brown, 9-14; Lepore, Ch. 16; Byrne got her Master on 1st June 1927, with the thesis "The Evolution of the Theory and Research on Emotions".

Marston had always been interested in cinema: while he was at Harvard, in 1915, he had participated in an Edison Company competition for the best screenplay written by a student. He won the prize with *Jack Kennard, Coward* and surpassed over 300 competitors.³³ Olive had two children from Marston, but she declared a marriage to 'William K. Richard'. At the time, when Byrne ran the house and Marston did casual jobs, Holloway's work supported the family. They spent their summers in Truro (Cape Cod) near Ethel Byrne's house and near the house that Margaret Sanger had bought from John Reed, in 1917, when he went to Russia to document the October Revolution. In the Summer 1935 the family moved to Cherry Orchard, a large house with lawn, a garden, cherry trees in Rye, New York. Byrne was staff writer for *Family Circle*, a weekly women's magazine which was distributed in stores since 1932. Like Olive Richard, she wrote articles where she interviewed William Marston, who showed his theories on emotions or explained the use of the Lie Detector. It really was advertising, but it would have resulted in an unpredictable change. Being inspired by Marston, John Larson and then Leonarde Keeler, improved the machine in the 1920s. Police departments purchased the 'polygraph' all over the country. Marston in vain published the book *The Lie Detector Test* in 1938 to claim his priority.³⁴

Paradise Island

In 1940 the Chicago Daily News published the short editorial "A National Disgrace (And a Challenge to American Parents)" which radically attacked comic books.³⁵ These magazines, warned Sterling North, full of Supermen, half-dressed women, automatic weapons and murders were contaminating young minds, growing a "generation even more ferocious than the present one". Nothing was saved, not even the colour print: "Their crude blacks and reds spoil the child's natural sense of color".³⁶

Even the dime novels, which according to North were "classic literature" compared to comic books, had been called as a "national shame" at the time.³⁷ Also the pulps, which had later replaced the dime novels, had been subject to regulations aimed to ban the spiciest from Newsstand.³⁸

The article, addressed to parents, and taken by numerous magazines, aroused a widespread feeling among teachers and librarians.³⁹ The possible rise of a puritanical wave aroused a different sentiment among comic book publishers, who saw a thriving market: according to an estimate in 1941 newsstands sold from seven to ten million comics every month, for an annual gross revenue of \$ 8-12 million. In the next years the monthly sales reached 15 million (1942) and 25 million (1943). Each illustrated book could also have five readers. Publishers published the illustrated books earlier than the cover date to increase the exhibition period.⁴⁰

³³ Lepore, Ch. 4.

³⁴ Ken Alder, *The Lie Detectors: The History of an American Obsession* (New York: Free Press, 2007), xiii, 146ff, 182.

³⁵ Sterling North, "A National Disgrace", *Chicago Daily News*, May 8, 1940.

³⁶ David Hajdu, *The Ten-Cent Plague: The Great Comic-Book Scare and How It Changed America* (Farrar, Straus and Giroux, 2008) 40-41.

³⁷ In *The Atlantic Monthly*, August 1906 (David Hajdu, *The Ten-Cent Plague*, 11, 41).

³⁸ In March 1934 Paul Moss, the relevant New York City official, banned the sale of "indecent" magazines. Douglas Ellis et al., ed., *The art of the pulps: an illustrated history* (San Diego, CA: IDW Publishing, 2017) 195.

³⁹ Amy Kiste Nyberg, *Seal of approval: the history of the comics code*, *Studies in popular culture* (Jackson [Miss.]: University Press of Mississippi, 1998) 6.

⁴⁰ David Hajdu, *The Ten-Cent Plague*, 45; Bradford W. Wright, *Comic book nation: the transformation of youth culture in America* (Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press, 2001) 31.

Harry Donenfeld (National Periodicals) and Charles Gaines (All-American Publications) decided to set up an Editorial Advisory Board with experts in the fields of “child psychology education, and welfare” to prevent criticism and reassure parents.

Family Circle in turn published an article: Olive Richard interviewed Marston, who proved an expert of this new mass media. “do you think these fantastic comics are good reading for children?” – She asked. According to Marston, Superman in particular represented the desire “to develop unbeatable national might, and to use this great power, when we get it, to protect innocent, peace-loving people from destructive, ruthless evil.”⁴¹ The Comics that showed violence were, however, more reprehensible, added Marston.

The hint at Superman was music to the ears of those who published it. Charles Gaines, a former teacher, was in charge of the committee and called Marston there. It included, among other, Pearl S. Buck, Nobel Prize winner; Josette Frank, staff advisor of the Children’s Book Committee of the Child Study Association; Robert Thorndyke, a professor in the Department of Educational Psychology at Columbia University. In addition, Dr. Lauretta Bender, child psychiatrist associated with New York’s Bellevue Hospital, showed a paper on comics at the annual meeting of the American Orthopsychiatric Association, held in New York in February 1941 where she appreciated comics for their “cathartic” effect. A few years later *The Journal of Educational Sociology* published the special issue “The Comics as an Educational Medium” (December 1944) with an article by Bender.⁴²

Marston advised Gaines that a female heroine would best represent the healthiest principles to be included in comics. He was convincing and, after Gaines’ approval, he drafted the first script in February 1941: “Suprema, the Wonder Woman”,⁴³ that editor Sheldon Mayer called only “Wonder Woman”. Marston hired and paid Harry G. Peter as a draughtsman, who was sixty years old, then.⁴⁴ Peter had lived in New York since 1907 and had met the feminist drawer Lou Rogers when he was working for a magazine *The Modern Woman* (1912-1917). Following Marston’s instructions, Peter prepared sketches.⁴⁵

Diana, the queen Hyppolite’s daughter and later known as Wonder Woman, wore a scantily dress in the colours of the American flag, a bodice, shorts and boots. She also had the bracelets that Olive used to wear and which Wonder Woman repelled bullets with. Hyppolite held the Magic Girdle. With its effect, thanks to the power that Aphrodite had infused, Amazons were immortal, until they left Paradise Island.⁴⁶ Like other superheroes, princess Diana puts on the second identity of Diana Prince, Colonel Darnell’s secretary at the Office of Military Intelligence in Washington.”⁴⁷

The first story “Introducing Wonder Woman”, about which we have already said, was published on All-Star Comics #8, December 1941 signed by “Charles Moulton”. According to Roy Thomas⁴⁸ the idea of anticipating the first release, scheduled on *Sensation Comics* #1, was a last minute decision: the script was reduced for the few pages available and the cover did not recall the new character.

⁴¹ “Don’t Laugh at the Comics” *Family Circle*, 25.10.1940. Cf. Lepore Ch. 22, Bunn 106.

⁴² David Hajdu, *The Ten-Cent Plague*, 45-46. Amy Kiste Nyberg, *Seal of approval*, 15-16. Frank will renounce his job because he does not approve the content of the comics in January 1942 (Lepore, Ch. 27 note 22). In February 1944 Bender will join the Committee (ibid. note 28). Bender, Lauretta «The Psychology of Children’s Reading and the Comics» *The Journal of Educational Sociology* 18, n. 4 (1944): 223–31. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2262695>

⁴³ After being hired as a writer, Marston left the Committee.

⁴⁴ Roy Thomas, *Wonder Woman: the war years 1941-1945* (New York: Chartwell Books, 2015), 9.

⁴⁵ An example can be seen in William Moulton Marston and H. G Peter, *Wonder Woman: The Complete Dailies 1944-1945*, 2014. 6.

⁴⁶ All-Star Comics #8, December 1941. Hyppolite’s girdle is also a legacy of the classical mythology, Morford, Mark O, and Robert J Lenardon. *Classical Mythology* 527.

⁴⁷ *Sensation Comics* #3, Marzo 1942, “A Spy in the Office”; here we see Diana Prince while she is operating a Lie Detector.

⁴⁸ Thomas, *Wonder Woman: the war years 1941-1945*, 9.

The story of the origins was a recurring theme in *Wonder Woman* #1 (Summer 1942): the archeologist, Dr. Hellas finds an old parchment manuscript — “The greatest find of modern times!...The history of the unconquerable Amazons!”. While Superman is the sole survivor of an alien world, the Amazons form a society that can replace the ‘Man’s World’; although historically the Greek myth depicted them as a negative example of what could have happened if women had come to power.⁴⁹ In a favourable context the myth transcends its origin and creates its identity:

Amazon society, as both mythology, history, and universal male nightmare, represents a culture in which women reign culturally supreme *because* of their sexual identity.

(Just as men have reigned culturally supreme because of *their* sexual identity.)⁵⁰

In December 7th, 1941 the Japanese air-sea powers attacked the American base at Pearl Harbor in Hawaii, causing the United States to enter the second World War. On several occasions Wonder Woman will fight the Axes military and their Fifth Column.

The monthly magazine *Sensation Comics* had published the next stories since January 1942. In one of them Diana receives from her mother a “Magic Lasso”⁵¹ which, thanks to its extraordinary powers, obliges those who are bound by it to tell the truth, a reference to Lie Detector that Marston liked particularly.

The success was immediate, if it is true that since July 1942 Wonder Woman had a dedicated magazine. Marston decided to leave his anonymity with the press release “Noted Psychologist Revealed as Author of Best-Selling Wonder Woman”.⁵² On several occasions Wonder Woman exceeded Superman’s sales.⁵³

Home Front

What were the “educational” themes that readers found in the adventures of the heroine at that time?

A significant story is “Battle for Womanhood”⁵⁴ where Wonder Woman’s opponent is Mars, the god of war, drawn as a Roman centurion. In more recent stories, starting from George Pérez’s reboot, Ares is more consistent with the Greek pantheon.⁵⁵

Mars, who had already appeared in a 1940 comic book, was a regular character of *Planet Comics* (Fiction House) from 1941 to 1945 when Mysta, a new heroine, defeated him.⁵⁶ Mars in *Wonder Woman*⁵⁷ is similar to the opponent of *Planet Comics* in Roman costume and mental powers. In “Mars God of War” (*Planet Comics* #15) Mars gets the mental control over an Axian dictator — a

⁴⁹ Lefkowitz, Mary R. *Women in Greek Myth*. Baltimore, Md.: Johns Hopkins Univ. Press, 2007, 4-5; Eva C Keuls, *The Reign of the Phallus: Sexual Politics in Ancient Athens* (New York: Harper & Row, 1985) 44-47; Jeannine Davis-Kimball, *Warrior Women: An Archaeologist’s Search for History’s Hidden Heroines* (New York: Warner Books, 2002) 112ff.

⁵⁰ Amazon Societies: Visions And Possibilities in Phyllis Chesler, *Women and Madness* (Garden City, N.Y: Doubleday, 1972), 284.

⁵¹ *Sensation Comics* #6, June 1942.

⁵² Lepore Ch. 26.

⁵³ Tim Hanley, *Wonder Woman Unbound: The Curious History of the World’s Most Famous Heroine* (Chicago: Chicago Review Press, 2014) 17.

⁵⁴ *Wonder Woman* (I Series) #5, June-July 1943.

⁵⁵ *Wonder Woman* (II Series) #1, February 1987; Ares, Mars in Phil Jimenez, John Wells, and William Moulton Marston, *The essential Wonder Woman encyclopedia: the ultimate guide to the Amazon princess* (New York: Del Rey/DC/Ballantine Books, 2010).

⁵⁶ *National Comics* #1 (Quality Comics, July 1940); *Planet Comics* (Fiction House) #15 (Nov.1941), #35 (Mar. 1945); Cf. Mitchell Maglio, Roy Thomas, and Hames Ware, *Fiction House: From Pulp to Panels, from Jungles to Space*, (2017) 20, 38-39. Issue #15 on-sale date was 1941-08-12, <https://www.comics.org/issue/1760/>

⁵⁷ *Wonder Woman* #1 (Summer 1942).

transparent image of Hitler — to spark off a war. Similarly, in *Wonder Woman #2* (Fall 1942) Mars controls Hitler's mind, to whom he addresses as "Earth Slave NZ-1". From the aforementioned article *Don't Laugh at the Comics* we know that Marston followed comic books. Olive's brother, Jack Byrne, was editor of Fiction House:⁵⁸ we can assume that Marston knew *Planet Comics* and considered Mars as the perfect character who would become Wonder Woman's arch-enemy. In "Battle for Womanhood", concerned about the role of women of the ongoing war against the Axis powers, Mars listens to a report:

"There are eight million American women in war activities— By 1944 there will be eighteen million!"

"Women! This smells like more of Aphrodite's work!...If women gain power in war they'll escape man's domination completely! They will achieve a horrible independence!"

"Wonder Woman's appearance in 1941 seemed to foreshadow some of the changes that came with the war in the limitations traditionally placed on women." Said Emily Yellin.⁵⁹

Mars subliminally influences Dr. Psycho, who in turn hates women, to discredit their work. Psycho hypnotizes his wife Marva, a psychic, and by means of her powers he causes accidents and sabotages to be imputed to the working women.

According to Lepore, Hugo Münsterberg, director of the Psychology Laboratory at Harvard in the years when Marston was a student, inspired Dr. Psycho. Münsterberg, coming from Germany, criticized the United States for too much equality of the sexes, citing as an example the women from his country who ran the house; he died in 1916, after backing the German cause in the first World War and so he lost his popularity.⁶⁰

After changeable struggles, Wonder Woman defeated Psycho and thus held talks with Marva:

"Submitting to a cruel husband's domination has ruined my life! But what a weak girl can do?"

"Get strong! Earn your own living — join the WAACS or WAVES and fight for your country! Remember the better you can fight, the less you'll have to!"

140,000 women joined the Women's Army Corps (WAC), 100,000 entered the navy as WAVES (Women Accepted for Voluntary Emergency Service).⁶¹

While Wonder Woman was piloting an ultra-fast⁶² invisible plane, since 1942 1102 women had participated in not-combat military missions. Having been classified as Women Airforce Service Pilots (WASP) since 1943, they delivered planes, towed targets, piloted the P-39 — which the male pilots called Flying Coffin — and the B-29 Superfortress; thirty-eight of them lost their lives. The WASP program was closed in December 1944 and women were discharged as simple civilians. Until President Carter signed the law that recognized them as veterans in 1977. In 2009 President Obama and Congress granted them the Congressional Gold Medal; among other reasons:

they faced overwhelming cultural and gender bias against women in nontraditional roles and overcame multiple injustices and inequities in order to serve their country;⁶³

In Pérez's reboot, Diana Rockwell, Steve Trevor's mother, will be one of these pilots.⁶⁴

Mars' fears were justified:

⁵⁸ Lepore Ch. 19; Maglio, Fiction House 22.

⁵⁹ Emily Yellin, *Our Mothers' War: American Women at Home and at the Front during World War II*, 2005, 105.

⁶⁰ Lepore, Ch. 3; Bunn 93.

⁶¹ Elaine Tyler May *Pushing the limits: 1940-1961* in Nancy F. Cott, ed., *No small courage: a history of women in the United States* 485-6.

⁶² Sensation Comics #1 (January 1942).

⁶³ Amy Nathan, *Yankee Doodle Gals: Women Pilots of World War II* (Washington, D.C.: National Geographic Society, 2001) 8-9, 20-21, 68, 73, 75, 84; <https://www.govinfo.gov/content/pkg/PLAW-111publ40/html/PLAW-111publ40.htm>

⁶⁴ "Echoes of the Past" Wonder Woman (II Series) #12, January 1988.

[The] number [of women] increased from 13,000,000 employed in 1940 to 18,150,000 in 1944 when women composed more than a third of the nation's working force. In the aircraft industry approximately 500,000 women were building bombers, transport and pursuit planes, dressed in overalls and handling the riveting machines as if they had been born to it. The number of women in metal, chemical and rubber increased by over 460 per cent between the prewar years and 1944. Ten per cent of all workers in shipyards, for example, were women although virtually no women had been employed in that industry before Pearl Harbor. Women's membership in trade unions more than quadrupled. Some 3,500,000 were members at the end of 1944 although there had been only 800,000 women in the trade unions in 1938.⁶⁵

Rosie the riveter became the symbol of women in the war industry.⁶⁶

The subject of the working women and of equal parity is tackled in the story "Department Store Perfidy"⁶⁷. The saleswomen employed in the department stores of the young and rich Gloria Bullfinch, go on strike because they are paid below the subsistence level. Diana, with her magic lasso, hypnotizes Gloria: "You will forget you are Gloria Bullfinch! When you awake you will be Ruth Smith, a poor girl looking for work." And sends her to work as a saleswoman in her own department store. After trying her own medicine and getting back to normal, Gloria improves the working conditions and doubles pays.

Before the second World War there was a double labour market: for women in the services, for men in the factories and in professions.⁶⁸

Many [women] had been employed before the war, mostly in low-paying, nonunion jobs in laundries, department stores, restaurant, and hotels, where they earned an average of \$24.50 a week, compared to \$40.35 a week for wartime manufacturing jobs.⁶⁹

Woman's independence, a subject dear to Amazons, pervades almost all stories.⁷⁰ If in "Amazon Bride"⁷¹ Diana imagines marrying Steve Trevor, on waking up she realizes to her relief it was a dream.

In 1937 Marston held a press conference where he envisaged that in the future women would rule the world and, providing a list of the people who had contributed most to humanity, he cited Margaret Sanger in second place immediately after Henry Ford and before F.D. Roosevelt. Associated Press and several newspapers took up again the news. Los Angeles Times wrote "FEMININE RULE DECLARED FACT."⁷²

Those who had remembered it would not have found the cover of *Wonder Woman* No. 7 (Winter 1943) entitled "Wonder Woman for President!" so strange. The Magic Sphere⁷³ - a large circular screen that can show the past and future events, for each place on the Earth - given by Athena to Queen Hyppolite, stands out among the highly advanced devices available to the Amazons from Paradise Island.

⁶⁵ Boyer, Richard Owen, & Herbert M Morais. *Labor's Untold Story*. New York: United Electrical, Radio & Machine Workers of America, 1997, 335.

⁶⁶ Sherna B Gluck, *Rosie the Riveter Revisited: Women, the War, and Social Change* (Boston: Twayne, 1987).

⁶⁷ Sensation Comics #8, Agosto 1942.

⁶⁸ Allison McNeill et al., *American Home Front in World War II* (Detroit: UXL, 2005) 108.

⁶⁹ Elaine Tyler May *Pushing the limits: 1940-1961* in Nancy F. Cott, ed., *No small courage: a history of women in the United States*, 476.

⁷⁰ In the story "The return of Diana Prince" Sensation Comics #9, September 1942 Wonder Woman, like Diana Prince, speaks to a woman and lets out: "I envy you yours [position] as wife and mother". But it is an exception to the rule.

⁷¹ Comic Cavalcade #8 (Autumn 1944).

⁷² Bunn 105, Lepore Ch. 21.

⁷³ All Star Comics #8, December 1941.

“Tomorrow happened yesterday.” - Says Hyppolite “Future events already exist because they are created by past events! Since our magic sphere records everything that has happened, it can predict everything that will happen in the future!”⁷⁴

Being tuned to 3000 A.D., Washington, the Sphere shows the future where women rule and the president is a woman. Not everything will be perfect: the cruel senator Heeman, head of the “Man’s World Party” plans a coup d’état:

“You women are feather-brained idealists! You’ve stopped us men from making money out of public office! You’ve taught people to elect officials who serve the public and expect nothing for themselves!”

In the future there will always be Wonder Woman: she defeats the senator and the new president will be Diana. “All men are much happier when their strong aggressive natures are controlled by a wise and loving woman!” – said Hyppolite, expounding one of Marston’s⁷⁵ favorite theories.

Alice Marble, an associate editor of *Wonder Woman* and a famous tennis champion, edited the supplement “Wonder Women of History” with life and facts of women such as Florence Nightingale, Madame Curie, Susan B. Anthony, Giovanna D’Arco.

In August 1942 ‘Olive Richard’ published another of her articles in the form of interview to Marston where “this psychological Nero Wolfe” expounded the theory in his comics:

“Boys, young and old, satisfy their wish thoughts by reading comics.” - “Wonder Woman and the trend toward male acceptance of female love power which she represents indicates that the first psychological step has actually been taken..”⁷⁶

Marston calls Olive “my Wonder Woman”

“Your bracelets...they’re the original inspiration for Wonder Woman’s Amazon chain bands.”⁷⁷ “Wonder Woman’s bracelets protect her against bullets in the wicked world of men.”

He shows a comic book where the heroine rejects the bullets fired by individuals “of definitely Teutonic cast” on board a speedboat⁷⁸ and says: “But she [Aphrodite] laid down the rule that they must never surrender to a man for any reason. I know of no better advice to give modern women than this rule that Aphrodite gave the Amazon girls.”

Since May 1944 King Features Syndicate (Hearst Corporation) had distributed Wonder Woman⁷⁹ strip to newspapers. Only superheroes like Superman and Batman had their daily strip, a sign of a great diffusion. At this point Marston was unlikely to write all the required stories and he hired Joye Hummel, his 19-year-old former pupil.⁸⁰ Among Hummel’s stories, “When Treachery Wore a Green Shirt” denounces an atmosphere of intolerance that was developing and that would then result in McCarthyism and in Red Scare.⁸¹

A few months later Marston fell seriously ill with polio and later with cancer. He died still young on February 5, 1947. Although Elizabeth Holloway had offered herself, National Comics assigned the

⁷⁴ Wonder Woman, #7, Winter 1943.

⁷⁵ Brown, «Love Slaves and Wonder Women», 31; Bunn, 104.

⁷⁶ Olive Richard, «Our Women Are Our Future», *Family Circle*, 14 August 1942. <http://www.angelfire.com/indie/jamietakot/Article3.htm>

⁷⁷ As already mentioned, in these articles ‘Olive Richard’ pretended to know Marston only as a journalist for *Family Circle*.

⁷⁸ Cover of Sensation Comics #3 March 1942.

⁷⁹ Marston and Peter, *Wonder Woman: The Complete Dailies 1944-1945* .

⁸⁰ Cf. Interview to Joye Hummel Murchison Kelly in Tom Young, «A Real Life Wonder Woman Adventure», *Smithsonian Libraries Unbound* (blog), 25 September 2015, <https://blog.library.si.edu/blog/2015/09/25/a-real-life-wonder-woman-adventure/>

⁸¹ Joye [Hummel] Murchison [as Charles Moulton], *Sensation Comics #81* (September 1948)

series to Robert Kanigher who belittled the character's feminism for the *romance* tones.⁸² Hummel, whose work Marston approved, will leave after the wedding. The comics code stated "The treatment of love-romance stories shall emphasize the value of the home and the sanctity of marriage...Divorce shall not...represented as desirable".⁸³ At the end of the war millions of American women, who had made an essential contribution to the victory, shared Wonder Woman's fate: women enlisted in the army or employed in the war industry had to come back to their homes to let men take their places. Women's average weekly pay declined from fifty dollars to thirty-seven dollars, a drop of 26 percent, more than five times the postwar decrease for men. Three quarters of the women who had jobs in war industries were still employed after the war, but 90 percent of them were earning less than they had during the war.⁸⁴ These data show that the double labor market had returned after the war, as Kessler-Harris and Hartmann analyzed;⁸⁵ "The more we learned about the wartime experience of women, the angrier we became about women's lost chances." Gluck wrote, while she was collecting their oral stories in the 1980s.⁸⁶ Tyler May introduced the concept of "Domestic Containment" for this social climate that linked Cold War policy to the domestic ideal.⁸⁷

⁸² Ruth McClelland-Nugent *The Amazon Mystique: Subverting Cold War Domesticity in Wonder Woman Comics, 1948-1965* in Chris York, *Comic Books and the Cold War: 1946-1962; Essays on Graphic Treatment of Communism, the Code and Social Concerns* (Jefferson, N.C.: McFarland, 2012) 115-128; Mike Madrid, *The Supergirls: Fashion, Feminism, Fantasy, and the History of Comic Book Heroines*, Revised & updated edition (Ashland, Oregon: Exterminating Angel Press, 2016), 54-55.

⁸³ Comics Magazine Association of America - Comics Code (1954) in Nyberg, Amy Kiste. *Seal of approval: the history of the comics code* 166-169.

⁸⁴ Elaine Tyler May *Pushing the limits: 1940-1961* in Nancy F. Cott, ed., *No small courage: a history of women in the United States* 493.

⁸⁵ Alice Kessler-Harris, *Out to Work: A History of Wage-Earning Women in the United States* 20th Anniversary Edition (New York: Oxford University Press, 2002) 286-287; Susan M Hartmann, *The Home Front and beyond: American Women in the 1940s* (Boston: Twayne Publishers, 1982) 24-26.

⁸⁶ Sherna B Gluck, *Rosie the Riveter Revisited*, x.

⁸⁷ Elaine Tyler May, *Homeward Bound: American Families in the Cold War Era* (Basic Books, 1988); Robinson, Lillian S. *Wonder Women: Feminisms and Superheroes*. Psychology Press, 2004, 47; Melissa A. McEuen, «Women, Gender, and World War II», *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of American History*, 9 June 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1093/acrefore/9780199329175.013.55>

The return of Amazons

Full ahead until 1972. Gloria Steinem, engaged in the feminist movement,⁸⁸ still remembered Wonder Woman comics she had read as a child:

Looking back now at these Wonder Woman stories from the '40s, I am amazed by the strength of their feminist message...Wonder Woman symbolizes many of the values of the women's culture that feminists are now trying to introduce into the mainstream.

Strength and self-reliance for women, sisterhood and mutual support among women; peacefulness and esteem for human life, a diminishment both of "masculine" aggression and of the belief that violence is the only way of solving conflicts.⁸⁹

In the sixties she dreamed of carrying out a musical on Wonder Woman.⁹⁰ In the first issue of the new magazine *Ms.* and to support a woman's candidacy, Shirley Chisholm, in the Democratic Party primary for the presidential campaign, Steinem took up again the "Wonder Woman for President" cover which we have already mentioned.⁹¹ In 2017 *Ms.* revived the Amazon heroine for the fifth time.

In the 70s those who had not known the forties comics could watch the adventures of Wonder Woman on TV. While the first season kept the feminism of the original stories, in the two following seasons the reasons for action and investigation typical of those years prevailed.⁹² The iconic Lynda Carter showed a new potential to the little girls. The original costume worn in the TV series was exhibited at the Metropolitan Museum of Art (New York) in 2008: "young women gasped excitedly...as though viewing the relics of a feminist patron saint".⁹³

Dc Comics decided to update the long-lived comics series, which arrived at No. 329. George Pérez rebooted texts and drawings in 1987 to emphasize the Greek mythology and the female, or else feminist, themes, contained in the old stories.⁹⁴ Several authors alternated, some of whom, like Gail Simone and Greg Rucka, kept the spirit of the character, perhaps more than others.

Born into a utopia of peace, she leaves of her own accord to enter a world at war, to fight against injustice on every level...to advocate that there is a better way for us to live. That a world of mutual respect and understanding is far better than one without; that a world of tolerance and equality is worth fighting for.

The latter wrote.⁹⁵ Mike Madrid defined Wonder Woman by Simone as

⁸⁸ Judith Harlan, *Feminism: A Reference Handbook* (Santa Barbara, Calif.: ABC-CLIO, 1998) 68.

⁸⁹ William Moulton Marston, *Wonder Woman: Introduction by Gloria Steinem. Interpretive Essay by Phillis Chesler. Designed by Bea Feitler.* (New York: Holt, Rinehart and Winston, 1972).

⁹⁰ Carolyn G Heilbrun, *The Education of a Woman: The Life of Gloria Steinem* (New York: Dial Press, 1995) 128

⁹¹ Amy Erdman Farrell, *Yours in Sisterhood: Ms. Magazine and the Promise of Popular Feminism* (Chapel Hill: The University of North Carolina Press, 1998) 53-55.

⁹² DVD Edition: Douglas S Cramer et al., *Wonder Woman: the complete collection*, 2007; Andi Zeisler, *Feminism and Pop Culture* (Berkeley, Calif.: Seal Press: Distributed by Publishers Group West, 2008) 78-80; Katherine J Lehman, *Those Girls: Single Women in Sixties and Seventies Popular Culture* (Lawrence, Kan.: University Press of Kansas, 2011) 186-193; Herbie J. Pilato, *Starlog Magazine* n. 260 (March) (1999) 53-58; Marc Andreyko et al., *Wonder Woman '77*. (Burbank, CA: DC Comics, 2016) is based on the TV Series.

⁹³ Jennifer K Stuller, *Ink-Stained Amazons and Cinematic Warriors: Superwomen in Modern Mythology* (London: I.B. Tauris, 2010) xiii; Andrew Bolton, Michael Chabon, Metropolitan Museum of Art (New York), *Superheroes: Fashion and Fantasy* (New York; New Haven: Metropolitan Museum of Art; Yale University Press, 2008); Mike Madrid, *The Supergirls: Fashion, Feminism, Fantasy, and the History of Comic Book Heroines* 293-294.

⁹⁴ George Pérez et al., *Wonder Woman by George Pérez Omnibus*, 2015 (reprint).

⁹⁵ Landry Q. Walker, *Wonder Woman: the ultimate guide to the Amazon warrior*, First American edition (New York, New York: DK Publishing, 2017) 7.

noble and courageous, a brilliant and confident warrior: a role model for her fellow superheroines. This version of Wonder Woman was warm, human, and, amazingly enough, had a sense of humor.⁹⁶

In 2016 DC Comics remembered 75 years since its creation with the reprint of old stories and special books. The *Wonder Woman* movie (2017) was a great success without betraying the original story message. “The original Marston comic book was the bible, particularly when it came to the spirit of what she stood for and who she is in the world.” said the director Patty Jenkins⁹⁷ working on the second *Wonder Woman 1984* film which will be released in the second middle of 2020. Biopic *Professor Marston and the Wonder Women* (2017) by Angela Robinson also aroused controversies over the introduction of undocumented biographical elements.⁹⁸ Till today Wonder Woman remains always the most famous superheroine.

⁹⁶ Mike Madrid, *The Supergirls: Fashion, Feminism, Fantasy, and the History of Comic Book Heroines* 219; Cf. Jennifer K Stuller, *Ink-Stained Amazons and Cinematic Warriors: Superwomen in Modern Mythology*, 151-152.

⁹⁷ Sharon Gosling and Patty Jenkins, *Wonder Woman: the art and making of the film*, First edition (London: Titan Books, 2017) 11; Aviva Dove-Viebahn, «Peace Strength Wisdom Wonder», *Ms. Magazine*, (Fall 2017) 30-33; <http://www.boxofficemojo.com/movies/?id=wonderwoman.htm>

⁹⁸ <https://www.psychologytoday.com/blog/beyond-heroes-and-villains/201710/the-true-story-wonder-womans-marston-m-nage-trois>

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